

Influence of Television Commercials on Child Psychology

Author's Details:

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Abstract:

This study investigates the influence of advertising and its impact on children psychology in Pakistan. It is also the main purpose of this empirical study is to examine the impact of specific objective is to see the causes of advertisement affecting on children psychology in a positive and negative sense both. Literature Review Reveals that children psychology plays a great role in selling of product through advertisement. Advertisement is the backbone for the company and product. As it is statically prove that through advertisement children are adopting the product. Now a day's child plays a vital role in society in increasing sales of the product and advertisement are more influencing on children. Targeted Population was parents and children and sample size was 201. To achieve the objectives primary data was collected through questionnaire and non-random sampling method was used. This study is limited to parents and children of few areas.

Keywords: *children psychology, advertisement, sound effects, animations, purchasing power, packaging design, viewing hours, food advertisement, favorite celebrity.*

1. Introduction:

Nowadays advertisement plays an important role in persuading customers to buy products and services. On the other hand the expenses of advertisement in comparisons of other activities in most companies are very remarkable. In the present days every company wants to achieve the highest market share. For this purpose every company use different ways to attract customers of different segments of the market and the best want to become a market leader. In this challenging environment a company should promote its products in such a way that more and more customers take interest in its products. Television is one of the strongest medium of advertisement. Due to its mass reach it can easily influence everyone, but children of course are the main victims of TV advertisements. Extent of TV influences varies from child to child, depending on factors like age, child's thinking viewing pattern that how much time they spent on TV. TV advertisements could be considered as a misleading communication but is also has some positive aspects. Television is a constant medium which is available at every time to every child. In the beginning children face so many problems to understand the message of the TV programs and advertisement. Exposure to television advertisements can influence children not only cognitively but also behaviorally. Certainly, advertisers who rely upon television advertisements have targeted several ages of children. Children are targeted by advertising agencies not only in home through television but in other contexts as well. The children acquire two information-processing skills in order to achieve full-grown understanding of advertising message. First, they must be able to discriminate at a perceptual level and second, they must understand the believable intent to advertising. In this research we have observe the impact of television advertisement on the children psychology. As a marketer to attract children toward the product it is necessary that the advertisement should contain such elements which are according to their age, mind set and interest for specific product. When children see the advertisement according to their interest, they persuade their parents to purchase that product. It holds very strong relationship between advertisement and psychology of children and we have tried to check the impact of advertisements on children through our research.

2. Problem statement:

To identify the effects of TV advertisements on children behavior.

3. Objectives of the research:

The following are the research objectives:

- To find out the relationship between child psychology and sound effects.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and animations.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and purchasing power.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and packaging design.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and viewing hours.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and food advertisements.
- To find out the relationship between child psychology and favorite celebrity.

4. Research Motivation & Contribution:

The purpose or motivation of this research is to quantify those TV commercials has influence on children buying psychology or not. We read different articles related to this topic and ask to many mothers and advertising agencies but some agreed with the fact that TV commercials have impact on children and some disagreed with this. Like that some researchers agreed and some disagreed. But most of the researchers agreed that TV advertisements have impact on children buying psychology.

5. Significance of the Study:

This type of research is necessary for every type of company who wants to boost their sales volume. This research is very important because if we know the results of the research then we will easily take the decisions accordingly. If result shows that TV advertisements have no impact on children psychology then companies should not take this step. The research in Pakistani context is very necessary because we usually do not see research on this topic in Pakistan. So this research may be helpful for companies in Pakistan because situations and circumstances of every country are different and in case of Pakistan this statement is hardly true and this research is needed. And it is also helpful for parents because through this research parents get to know that which type of advertisement their children can see and how much time they should allow their children to watch TV.

6. Literature Review:

The purpose of this literature review is to understand the impact of TV commercials on children's buying psychology. TV is the most dominant medium that marketers use to promote their products. Companies have the most efficient and effective way to attract their customers and that is the advertising of their products through television. Every company wants help of advertising agencies to create the awareness of their product among the people that what is the usage of a particular product and how much that product is important in our life.

Now a day's most of the advertising agencies are targeting children through the ads of chocolates, toys, ice creams & etc because they know that children plays an important role in the decision of buying process of their family (Kamal and Syed, 2014). Children can easily get influenced by the TV advertisement so the marketers and ad agencies should understand the psyche of children before launching any product or advertisement.

Children constitute a major customer market, with direct purchase power for food, drink and sweets and indirect influence while shopping for big-ticket items. Today parents have become more depending on kid's choices. The marketers try to make ads which influence children because they are not mature, their minds and abilities are not grown up as adults (Kamal and Syed, 2014). Advertising agencies now a day's using such appealing facts that are according to their age, mind and interest in order to attract the children. When children see advertisement according to their interest they persuade their parents to purchase that product.

Children also get influenced by watching commercials in school exhibitions and on internet (Kunkel and Dowrick, 2004). Many corporations now have introduced kids clubs for the direct communication and have

built the strong relationship with children because kids clubs give them more segmentation by the help of sending the direct mails, birthday cards to the children.

Most of the time commercials are not good for those who are spending their lives in a hand to mouth situation and they are not able to buy that product for which their children are persuading (Rehman and Hyder, 2014). Sometimes this situation turns into the alarming or critical situation because at that time children become aggressive and violent in order to fulfill their demand of purchasing particular product towards which they are attracted through commercials.

Television plays an important role in the process of purchasing advertised products due to children. TV advertisement can also create wrong perceptions among children about the nutritional values of foods and how to maintain good health because more than 80% of advertisements are related to food products (Harris and Brownell, 2010). Children are severely targeted by food marketers and confronted with an increasing number of commercials during TV programs, which aim at influencing their brand preference, choices, food purchases and intake (Haroon and Nisar, 2011). Watching food advertisements on TV greatly influence the children's behavioral practices, such as unhealthy dietary habits, purchase requests for high-calorie low-nutrient products and obesity.

It is indicated that the highly advertised products are of soft drinks, fast foods, sweets and other high calorie foods of poor nutritional value (Harris and Brownell, 2010). Since children are very much interested in the food messages presented in the TV commercials, misconception about the healthiness of the advertised products may develop, and they start consuming those products instead of fruits and vegetables consequently.

Children are easily get influenced by the commercials of snacks and ice-creams and they identify that particular brand in market through packaging or by telling the cartoon character or punch line of that advertisement to the shopkeeper (Willcox and Linn, 2004).

Food advertisements highly impact the eating behavior of children, because most of the parents do not buy the same food products because of the medical or health issues for the reason that the immune system of children who is about 3-6 years old are not strong enough (Abideen and Salaria, 2009). Their immune systems are not ready to accept the unhealthy foods as compared to the elders and due to these children suffer from many health issues.

The other main reason due to which the children force their parents to buy a particular product is the packaging of the product. Packaging includes the features, design or the colors that are used in that product (Parhizkar and Nazari, 2011). Children get attracted towards the packaging of the product by watching the advertisement of that product on television. If parents buy any food product which is requested by their children then children make their habit to buy and eat those food product in their daily routine then the end result is not good for them because after some times this habit changes into health problems like obesity and children also become overweight (Sadiq, 2015).

Children under the age of eight are not able to understand the televised advertising messages and are always ready to accept advertiser message as truthful, accurate and fair (Abideen and Salaria, 2009). This is a severe alarm because the most common products which are marketed to children are candies, soft drinks, sweets, sodas and snack foods. Advertising of such unhealthy food products to young children contributes to poor nutritional habits that may last for a lifetime.

Children's watching span also matters and affects the children psychology. In Pakistan, children who watch one hour program on television they probably see 15 edible advertisements during that program and when they watch television for 4 hours a day, they see one product advertisement around 20 times, it means that during one hour program a lot of food products are advertised on television which influence children to buy these

products on their own or ask their parents to buy the same for them (Nithya and Virmani, 2015). Repeated exposure of the advertisements may create a strong desire for the advertised products as compared to competitive products. The products such as toys, cereals and ice creams have a longer impact even if the frequency of these advertisements is limited to one per program because children's product knowledge primarily based on TV advertisements (Kamal and Syed, 2014).

Most of the advertising agencies are showing the children's favorite cartoon character or stars in their advertisement now a day because they know that children are easily influenced by this. (Nithya and Virmani, 2015). Children not only get influenced by those advertisements but they also make an effort to imitate like them when they see the advertisement and some children also become aggressive during or after watching the advertisement because advertisers show super human action in their advertisements.

Kids today have more self-sufficiency and decision making power than the previous generations which has made them more vocal about what they want their parents to do (Thakur, 2014). Children may not be the active buyers but they have a voice that influences the purchase of products. Children notice music, jingles, food item color and over all packaging of the brands through advertisements. The insight into children's awareness of advertisements has been gained. The young children who are between the ages of 7-11 years understand the message of TV advertising (Kunkel and Linn, 2004). Children are learning of specific product and brand knowledge makes them informed about consumers at their level. The acknowledgement of advertising message works as an external stimulus to children so they start convincing their parents and caretakers to buy their desired products.

Television commercials are also influencing the teenagers who are between the 13-19 years of age. Increased exposure to television programs or advertisement put teenagers at higher risks of adopting unhealthy lifestyle habits (Kunkel and Linn, 2004). Television advertisements impact both the genders equally. The product choice they make and how they see their gender role changes with television advertisements. Young females want to be like attractive spokespersons as she watches on television advertisements and on the other hand young males put more stress on becoming muscular like one of those male models who are in the advertisements. Youth often get carried away in the product choice when they see a celebrity endorsing a particular product (Willcox and Dowrick, 2004). Young children are more influenced by the TV advertisements as compared to other age groups. And they generally believe in what advertisements have to say about the products. If the advertisements are not very complex, and it says something new then, likelihood of attracting children's attention would increase (Kunkel and Linn, 2004). Youth and children often try to adopt role models, or characters presented in the commercials because they are exposed as smart, powerful and attractive in appearance and extravagant lifestyles.

Celebrity endorsement is an effective method of creating value and identification for a brand. Because of this reason celebrities are frequently used in television advertising to persuade children to try foods (Borzekowski and Robinson, 2001). TV commercials, including celebrity endorsement, play a dominant role in shaping children's product preference. Indeed, TV advertising first catch the attention of the children, then create interest in their minds about the product seen through the advertisement, then develop a desire to have that product, then children acquire the product by buying it or forcing their parents to buy it. Celebrities in these become the role models for the children in this age whether financially, professionally or with respect to image (Kamal and Syed, 2014). The power of their voice acts as an incredibly influential brand image tool in the market, particularly for the younger demographic. Children don't seek complex explanations to choose the brand they simply wish to be like their role models. Celebrity endorsement has the power to inspire, enlighten and entertain the consumer.

An advertisement also enhances the materialism because it is designed to stimulate the desires for the product that would not otherwise be the most important (Abideen and Salaria, 2009). Advertising propagates the

thought that wealth is important and that desirable qualities, such as beauty, success and happiness can be obtained only by materialistic goods.

TV commercials do not leave only negative impact on children memory and behavior, it also has some positive points because television commercial is an important information source for new commercials (Kashif and Abeer, 2012).TV advertisements are still the most popular media to reach children. TV advertisements have positive influence on the food preference of children.Children make them able to understand the complex messages through the advertisements (Abideen and Salaria, 2009).

In spite of other factors, packaging of product also impacts the children buying decision. Now a day's packaging has become itself a sales promotion tool for the companies. The children buying psychology also inspired by the packaging (color, wrapper, product design and other packaging characteristics) when they watch it in TV commercials. It stimulates the impulse buying psychology in children.

Advertisements which contain a large number of visual changes in scene, action and characters and have fast-paced production features such as rapid cutting between camera shots , zooming in and out of close ups and fading the picture up or down to a brighter or darker level of lightning can hold the child's visual attention (Borzekowski and Robinson, 2001). On an auditory level, lively music, sound effects, unusual voices, children's and women's voices and laughter are all effective for maintaining attention.

Children often monitor television advertisements via the sound track even when they are looking away from the screen (Borzekowski and Robinson, 2001). When their interest is triggered, they will turn to look at the screen again and maintain eye contact with it for as long as the advertisement captures their interest.

Music plays an important role in this process as it does both attract and hold the young viewer's attention, and increase the likelihood of repeat viewing and listening whenever the advertisement appears, enhancing its potential impact (Nithya and Vermani, 2015). The impact of music will varies from advertisement to advertisement and it is not reasonable to expect that the relationship between music and consumer response will be constant.

Understanding of the nature of TV advertisements appears to improve as children get older; belief in the truthfulness of advertising appeals tends to decline (Kamal and Syed, 2014). Before children begin school, there is widespread belief among young viewers that TV advertisements tell the truth all the time. The advertising industry can therefore begin to suffer from reliability gap among quite young children.

At the same time children's attempt to force parents to buy advertised products seen on television show is a marked decline (Waqas and Umair, 2014). In general, it seems that as children grow older they understand more completely the selling motive underlying television advertising and become less responsive to advertisements appeal. Amount of exposure to advertising was positively related to the perceived truthfulness of commercial (Kashif and Abeer, 2012).

When children watch young adults in good shape eating junk foods in the advertisements they imagine that it is good for the health (Sadiq, 2015). They do not know that junk food is not favorable to health. They are unaware of the fact that junk food does not contain nutritional value. They may even think that by eating these junk foods they might shape the same appearance as models in the advertisements. Childhood obesity is on the rise and one of the main reasons for this has been seen as excessive consumption of fast food and junk food. It has also been seen that childhood diabetes is also on the rise (Harris and Brownell, 2010).

Children may annoy their parents for the products which are advertised on television (Thakur, 2014). They may insist their parents to purchase that product which they have seen on television advertisements and may not give attention to the products which are better than that product. They may also insist on living a life as portrayed in advertisements.

Children may make excessive demands to their parents for the products they see in the advertisements (Kunkel and Linn, 2004). At times, they cry, pinch, pull and do not keep quiet till the parents purchase the product. Some parents who cannot control their children may give in to the tantrums of children left with no choice.

Previously advertisers marketed children's products towards parents. Parents were their targeted audience for these products (Thakur, 2014). But nowadays; marketers aim their messages directly at children. Advertisements are made specifically in such a way that they draw the attention of children. The marketing messages are aimed directly at the children because they know children can easily convince their parents to buy a product.

Music plays a vital role in the interactive process of consumer behavior. The commercial uses of music in marketing accounts for billions nationwide (Nithya and Vermani, 2015). Advertising agencies use music and colors to affect children behavior, music is one of their most important considerations and expense. Music presence has positively affected the product preference because when the music fits, the message processing of the advertisements will be externally enhanced (Parhizkar and Nazari, 2011). By the help of music or sound effects in advertisements children can easily recall and recognize the product of the particular brand, that's why the sound effects or music in advertisements is also known as the "Catalyst Of Advertising".

The use of music in general, must be carefully chosen by the advertising agencies for the products which are specially advertised for the children because music has been observed as both, positively and negatively, to stimulate a variety of responses including attention, mood, and attitude and purchase intention.

7. Conceptual Framework:

8. Variable Description:

8.1 Children behavior:

Children are very innocent and they don't know about the realities of world. They just do what they like to do. This is the reason due to which the children psychology is being changed very frequently. Children get easily attracted towards any toy or product because of their colors or presentation, that's why children get easily attracted towards TV advertisements also. TV advertisements are the main reason behind the change of children behavior. Any product which is advertised through television for children, becomes more popular and

demanding because the notice of advertising message works as an external stimulus to children so they start forcing their parents to buy that product for them. Today, children have more decision-making power and self-sufficiency than previous era which has made them more presentable about what they want their parents to buy.

8.2 Sound effect:

Sound Effect which is used in television advertisements by advertising agencies has impact on children behavior. Because children are mostly attracted towards television when they hear any song, music or their favorite jingle. Due to this reason most of the advertising agencies use rock music, song or jingles in their advertisements to gain the attention towards a particular product. Music plays an important role in the interactive process of consumer behavior. Most of the retailers did not want advertising agencies to use music or sound effects in their product advertisement but now the retailers also agree that music is one of their most vital considerations and expenses.

8.3 Animations:

Animation in television advertisements has impact on children behavior. As the world is moving towards the technology. It is important for a business or Production Company to stay connected with the era. The children of this era like animated movies or advertisements more than the live production, because of the colors or characters of animated advertisements. An amazing option these days is creating animated advertisements. It enables the company to say what they want. Animation will save company's time and money and it gives the chance to think out of the box. If anyone wants their character to grow thirty arms after taking a sip of energy drink to impress the children in order to raise the demand of any particular energy drink, they will be able to do that by the means of the creative tools we have today.

8.4 Purchasing Power:

Purchasing power has relation with children behavior. Now days the market for the children's food and products are massive. Parents at one side facing hard time in raising their children the way they want to, while on the other hand children are being increasingly influenced by television advertisements that often go against what parents want to do. The families which are spending their lives in hand to mouth situation are not able to fulfill all the wishes of their children or buy a product for them which are advertised in the advertisements for children.

8.5 Packaging Design:

Packaging design is the factor which impact children behavior so much. Packaging design include the color, features and shape of the product. Every company wants to give the best packaging design for their children patterns, because children do not pick the product from market because of the name of the product, they only pick the product by seeing its packaging which they watch in the television advertisement.

8.6 Viewing Hours:

Viewing hours have influence on children behavior. The children who watch more television knows the more about the products or advertisement. Sometimes it has negative impact also but at the same time it makes the children memory stronger and gives them chance to gain the knowledge.

8.7 Food Advertisement:

Food advertisements have impact on children psychology and health because more than half of the food items which are presented in television advertisements are rich in fat and sugar. Children ask their parents to buy that food product which they watch in advertisement. It affects children's unhealthy food consumption because most of the food advertisements are of candies, chips, chocolates and snacks.

8.8 Favorite Celebrity:

Favorite celebrity in television advertisement has so much impact on children's psychology because whenever they watch their favorite celebrity in advertisement they become excited and start forcing their parents to buy the product only because of that celebrity who is appeared in the advertisement. Advertising agencies now

emphasis more on this factor because they know children prefer the advertisement which are endorsed by their favorite celebrity and because of doing this their product demand also being increased.

9. Methodology:

9.1. Sample size: Questionnaires filled from different geographic areas in Karachi Pakistan. Through online Google forms and do non-random sampling technique was used.

9.2. Response Rate: We used 201 questionnaires, and respondents filled all of them, which indicate that response rate is 100%.

9.3. Research design: Quantitative research method approach was used, in which structured questionnaires were distributed which are based on the study which made by us. We used the quantitative research method because previous researches on this topic have already been done in quantitative nature.

9.4. Data Collection Method: The data collection tools which we used including the questionnaire which is designed on the basis of different questions which were filled by children and parents who told us what the impact of TV advertisements on children psychology is.

9.5. Statistical Techniques:

Ordinary least square regression analysis was applied because we have to check the dependency of “Children Behavior” on some TV advertisement variables such as “Sound Effect”, “Animation”, “Food Advertisements”, “Purchasing Power”, “Packaging Design”, “Viewing Hours”, “Favorite Celebrities”. This analysis explains how a dependent variable changes with the change in an independent variable at the same time keeping other independent variables constant.

9.6. Data Sources:

Secondary data collected through articles from the internet, websites, and research journals. primary data collected through questionnaire. Sampling Technique and Sample Size is 201 questionnaires were distributed in Karachi, Pakistan. All the respondents filled the questionnaire through Google forms. Responses are classified into seven determinants such as “Sound Effects”, “Animation”, “Purchasing Power”, “Packaging Design”, “Viewing Hours”, “Food Advertisement”, “and Favorite Celebrity”. An analysis was carried out to measure whether significant difference exists between the selected determinants or not.

10. Research Questions:

On the basis of above literature review we have developed following research questions.

- 1) What is the impact of sound effects on child psychology?
- 2) What is the impact of animations on child psychology?
- 3) What is the impact of purchasing power on child psychology?
- 4) What is the impact of packaging on child psychology?
- 5) What is the impact of viewing hours on child psychology?
- 6) What is the impact of food advertisements on child psychology?
- 7) What is the impact of favorite celebrity on child psychology?

11. Hypotheses:

On the basis of above research questions we have developed following research hypotheses

H1: Sound effects have an impact on children behavior.

H2: Animation has an impact on children behavior.

H3: Purchasing power has an impact on children behavior.

- H4:** Packaging designs have an impact on children behavior.
- H5:** Viewing hours has an impact on behavior.
- H6:** Food advertisements have an impact on children behavior.
- H7:** Favorite celebrities have an impact on children behavior.

12. Results:

The results for this research has been finalized by doing the reliability test and regression analysis through statistical software SPSS in order to find out the relationship between the television advertisements and children buying behavior.

12.1. Reliability Analysis:

Reliability analysis is carried out to verify the reliability of data that whether the conclusions and analysis perform for the data are reliable to understand and forecast. We used the common technique for assessing the reliability and that technique is Cronbach’s Alpha for internal reliability of the data set.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.838	8

The above table shows the test result of reliability analysis. The value of Cronbach’s Alpha is given by **0.838**; the number of items in the data set is **8**. The value associated with Alpha is said to be good and the conclusions draw from this data is very much reliable to understand and forecast.

12.2 Multiple Regression Analysis:

Multiple Regression Analysis was carried out to assess the relationship between one dependent variable and several independent variables.

The results of multiple regression analysis are presented below the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations.

12.3 Hypotheses :

12.3.1 Hypothesis 1:

H1: Sound effects have impact on children psychology.

The above hypothesis was tested through the regression analysis and the summarized results are presented below:

Table No. 1

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.502 ^a	.252	.248	.83690

a. Predictors: (Constant), Sounds Effects Total

The value of R in Table No.1 is 0.502 and R square is 0.252. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.252 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 2

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	46.993	1	46.993	67.095	.000 ^b
Residual	139.379	199	.700		
Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Sounds Effects Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 46.993 and the residual sum of squares 139.379. The value of F test is 67.095 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology.

Table No. 3

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.765	.184		9.610	.000
	Sounds Effects Total	.487	.060	.502	8.191	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The above table No. 3 gives the regression constant and coefficient and their significance. We see that P values for regression coefficient of sound effects 0.000 which is less than 0.05. It means we have accepted our hypothesis. It also shows the sound effect has an influence on child psychology. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model.

12.3.2. Hypothesis 2:

H2: Animation has impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Animation” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 4

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.411 ^a	.169	.165	.88209

a. Predictors: (Constant), Animation Total

The value of R in Table No.4 is 0.411 and R square is 0.169. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.169 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 5

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	31.532	1	31.532	40.525	.000 ^b
Residual	154.839	199	.778		
Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Animation Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 31.532 and the residual sum of squares 154.839 The value of F test is 40.525 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology.

Table No. 6

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.885	.214		8.808	.000
	Animation Total	.425	.067	.411	6.366	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.4 is 0.411 and R square is 0.169. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.5 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 31.532 and the residual sum of squares 154.839. The value of F test is 40.525 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H2. Table No. 6 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H2.

12.3.3. Hypothesis 3:

H3: Purchasing power has impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Purchasing Power” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 7

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.408 ^a	.167	.163	.88341

a. Predictors: (Constant), Purchasing Power Total

The value of R in Table No.7 is 0.408 and R square is 0.167. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.167 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 8

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	31.071	1	31.071	39.813	.000 ^b
Residual	155.301	199	.780		
Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Purchasing Power Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 31.071 and the residual sum of squares 155.301 The value of F test is 39.813 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology.

Table No. 9

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.769	.234		7.573	.000
	Purchasing Power Total	.472	.075	.408	6.310	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.7 is 0.408 and R square is 0.167. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.8 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 31.071 and the residual sum of squares 155.301. The value of F test is 39.813 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H3. Table No. 9 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H3.

12.3.4. Hypothesis 4:

H4: Packaging designs have impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Packaging Design” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 10**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.350 ^a	.123	.118	.90651

a. Predictors: (Constant), Packaging Design Total

The value of R in Table No.10 is 0.350 and R square is 0.123 The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.123 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 11**ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.840	1	22.840	27.794	.000 ^b
	Residual	163.531	199	.822		
	Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Packaging Design Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 22.840 and the residual sum of squares 163.531 The value of F test is 27.794 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology.

Table No. 12**Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.015	.232		8.694	.000
	Packaging Design Total	.388	.074	.350	5.272	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.10 is 0.350 and R square is 0.123. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.11 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 22.840 and the residual sum of squares 163.531. The value of F test is 27.794 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H4. Table No. 12 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H4.

12.3.5. Hypothesis 5:

H5: Viewing hours has impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Viewing Hours” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 13

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.457 ^a	.209	.205	.86078

a. Predictors: (Constant), Viewing Hours Total

The value of R in Table No.13 is 0.457 and R square is 0.209 The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.209 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 14

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.923	1	38.923	52.532	.000 ^b
	Residual	147.448	199	.741		
	Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Viewing Hours Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 38.923 and the residual sum of squares 147.448 The value of F test is 52.532 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology.

Table No. 15

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.689	.216		7.828	.000
	Viewing Hours Total	.486	.067	.457	7.248	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.13 is 0.457 and R square is 0.209. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.14 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of

square value is 38.923 and the residual sum of squares 147.448. The value of F test is 52.532 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H5. Table No. 15 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H5.

12.3.6. Hypothesis 6:

H6: Food advertisements have impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Food Advertisements” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 16

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.320 ^a	.102	.098	.91682

a. Predictors: (Constant), Food Advertisement Total

The value of R in Table No.16 is 0.320 and R square is 0.102 The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.102 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 17

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.099	1	19.099	22.721	.000 ^b
	Residual	167.273	199	.841		
	Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Food Advertisement Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 19.099 and the residual sum of squares 167.273 The value of F test is 22.721 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology

Table No. 18

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.262	.205		11.029	.000
	Food Advertisement Total	.325	.068	.320	4.767	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.16 is 0.320 and R square is 0.102. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.17 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 19.099 and the residual sum of squares 167.273. The value of F test is 22.721 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H6. Table No. 18 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H6.

12.3.7. Hypothesis 7:

H7: Favorite celebrities have impact on children psychology.

Analysis of hypothesis was carried out to measure the relationship of independent variable “Food Advertisements” and dependent variable “Children Behavior”. The hypothesis developed in this context is presented below:

Table No. 19

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.257 ^a	.066	.061	.93523

a. Predictors: (Constant), Favorite Celebrity Total

The value of R in Table No.19 is 0.257 and R square is 0.066 The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. Here the value of R-square is 0.066 that means the independent variable of model can be predicted 25.2% of the variance by the dependent variable. Adjusted R-square gives the more accurate information about the model fitness if one can further adjust the model by his own.

Table No. 20

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.317	1	12.317	14.082	.000 ^b
	Residual	174.055	199	.875		
	Total	186.371	200			

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), Favorite Celebrity Total

The above table gives the test result for the analysis of one way anova. The results are given in three rows. These values show the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 12.317 and the residual sum of squares 174.055 The value of F test is 14.082 significant at α 0.000. This shows the hypothesis is accepted so it means sound effect has an influence on child psychology

Table No. 21

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.256	.257		8.766	.000
	Favorite Celebrity Total	.309	.082	.257	3.753	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Children Behavior Total

The value of R in Table No.19 is 0.257 and R square is 0.066. The value of R shows a positive relation between variables. The Table No.20 shows the sum of squares for regression, residual and total. The regression sum of square value is 12.317 and the residual sum of squares 174.055. The value of F test is 14.082 significant at α 0.000. This shows the models goodness of fit in explaining the variations. This validates our alternative hypothesis H7. Table No. 21 shows the beta values of constant and the variables in the model. The beta values show the importance of each variable in the model. The value of t for preparedness is well above +2 which makes it a useful predictor. Hence we accept H7.

13. Conclusion:

The focus of the study was to determine the impact of TV advertisements on children's psychology. The children's psychology can easily be influenced by the packaging design, animations, celebrities and sound effects which are used in the advertisement of the product by advertising agencies. In today's media oriented society almost every child is bombarded with television advertisements. By the help of the data which we gathered from the respondents of Karachi, shows that children are much aware about the brands and their product because of the television commercials, and now they can easily differ the brands and products when they go to super markets or malls. It is clear that if advertisements are created efficiently they can become an effective media to convey the message among the children. Daily exposure to television advertisements has a remarkable impact upon attitude, food intake, purchases and actions of children.

14. Recommendation:

Some are the following recommendations on the basis of study.

- Viewing hours of television should be restricted i.e. less than to 1 or 2 hour per day. Parents should indulge their children in other fun activities.
- Parents should not place a television in personal rooms of their children, if the child is not immature.
- Parents should discuss television advertisement's educational values with their children.
- Children must know the difference between fantasy and reality.
- Advertising agencies should convey the positive message for children through their television advertisements.
- Advertising agencies should understand the mind of children before launching TV advertisement of any product.

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